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INNOVATION FOR TOMORROW: PROGRESS IN SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE CONCEPTS

ABSTRACT BOOK

of the biological hierarchy, from sub-individual (molecular and biochemical) to individual and population level. At molecular level, the modulation of the expression of different genes involved in oxidative stress (cat and sod), physiological and behavioral pathways (flot, SERCA and JHE) was assessed. At biochemical level the onset of oxidative stress (activity of antioxidant and detoxification enzymes, and lipid peroxidation) and changes in energy reserves were explored. Changes in body growth and swimming activity were investigated to assess effects at individual level, while reproductive effort was assessed as endpoint at population level. Our results showed that the exposure to wMPs obtained from both conventional and bioplastic objects induced effects at all considered levels of biological hierarchy. Interestingly, the strongest effects were recorded at population level where all the wMPs lead to a modulation in the reproductive effort. In detail, PS and PLA exposure lead to an increase in the number of offspring, PBAT lead to a reduction in the produced newborns and no effect were highlighted for PE. These results suggest the necessity to study in-depth the toxicity of wMPs.

1.09.B.T-04 Developing the Grouping of Polymers to Streamline Toxicology Testing

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Polymers are used across various industries, in everything from medical devices and packaging to automotive components and electronics. However, their diverse manufacturing processes, chemical structures, interactions with other substances, complex degradation processes, and limited toxicity data, make their hazard assessment complicated. Given the impracticality of individual animal testing for each polymer due to cost, time and animal use, there is a critical need to streamline toxicity assessments to better manage the environmental and health risks. Grouping is an approach that streamlines hazard assessment by providing evidence of similarity between substances so that animal hazard data can be read-across (shared) from one group member to another. This poster introduces a novel strategy integrating the existing grouping framework (from the EU project GRACIOUS) by replacing nano-specific elements with polymer-specific considerations. A polymer grouping hypothesis template has been developed which includes consideration of the purpose of grouping (e.g. regulatory), the lifecycle of polymers (to identify relevant exposure scenarios), and answers the fundamental questions of what they are (physicochemical characteristics), where they go (fate and behaviour in the environment, toxicokinetics), and what they do (hazards). The developed hypothesis template used to determine the dermal exposure to Polyacrylic Acid (PAA) in household detergents with a molecular weight of 4500 Da does not imply skin sensitization. The findings support the acceptance of the hypothesis, showing that PAA exhibits low dermal toxicity, no sensitizing potential, and mild eye irritation in rabbits. These results suggest a minimal human health risk through skin contact. It demonstrates the practical application of the framework and highlights future directions for research and implementation.

1.09.C Impact of Micro- and Nanoplastics on Environmental and Human Health: Monitoring, Fate, Exposure, Toxicity and Mechanisms of Toxic Action

1.09.C.T-01 Nanoplastics Selectively Bind and Unveil Novel Ragweed Pollen Allergens

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The pollen of *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*, ragweed pollen, is widespread cause of respiratory allergic reactions. The aim of the work was to provide evidence of corona formation and its properties on NP particles in simulated lung fluids (SLF), simulating event of pollen and NP co-exposure through respiration. *A. artemisiifolia* pollen is chosen as model system for investigation of NPs interactions with respiratory allergens. Its extract was prepared under mild conditions and short exposure to water, simulating rainfall burst of pollen particles. The binding of *Ambrosia* pollen allergens to NPs (PP and PET, 100 nm) was monitored in simulated lung fluids (SLF) by corona formation and mass spectrometry, while the effect of NPs on *Ambrosia* pollen proteins structure was studied by CD spectroscopy. Corona formation was analyzed by glycoproteins staining and immunoblotting with *Ambrosia* pollen allergic patients sera. Relevant NPs binding proteins of ragweed were also identified by shotgun proteomics in subpollen particles. *Ambrosia* pollen NPs corona is composed of specific allergenic proteins in SLF conditions showing highly selective binding of ragweed pollen proteins from the extract. Composition of soft and hard coronae is different between nanoPET and nanoPP particles. Hard corona of nanoPP is dominated by a low Mw glycopeptide(s). We have confirmed that 28-32 kDa proteins of hard corona are PCC13-62-like protein and plant basic secretory protein. We have also confirmed their presence in

subpollen particles. Specific adsorption of novel ragweed proteins and glycopeptides to NPs hard corona have been shown, allowing us to suggest those IgE-binding proteins and peptides to be major biocorona component of NPs. Our data provide insight into molecular events occurring during co-exposure of NPs and allergens. Selective binding of allergenic proteins to NPs may during co-exposure change the route of allergen exposure to the immune system and modulate allergic reactions. Funding from Horizon 2020, No965173, IMPTOX, by Ministry of Science, Innovation and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia, grant No451-03-66/2024-03/200168 and Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, GA F-26.

1.09.C.T-02 Polyvinyl Chloride- and Polypropylene-Model-Micro- and Nanoplastics Exhibit Different Mechanisms of Toxicity in Human Umbilical Vein Endothelial (HUVECs) Cells

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Plastic pollution, particularly in the form of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), has become a significant concern for both environmental and human health. Alarmingly, MNPs have been detected in human placental tissue, raising serious concerns about potential maternal-fetal exposure and its implications for fetal development. It is expectable that these small particles in the maternal bloodstream can be transferred to the fetal circulation and influence children's future lives. Since Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and polypropylene (PP) are dominant plastic types in environmental samples, we used model-MNPs made of these polymers labeled with fluorescent-quantum dots (qDs). To investigate the effects of these potentially circulating polymers at a fetal level, we used Human Umbilical Vein Endothelial Cells (HUVECs) as cell model, as representative of structural and biological barrier. Cytotoxicity assays revealed a concentration- and time-dependent decline in cell viability, with PP exerting a more pronounced effect, particularly at higher concentrations and extended exposure. Flow cytometry and confocal microscopy analyses further uncovered differential cellular responses. PVC-treated cells exhibited significant morphological changes, characterized by increased complexity and granularity, alongside elevated colocalization of MNPs with cellular membranes. In contrast, PP-treated cells demonstrated lesser internalization and predominantly surface-associated interactions. Z-stack fluorescence analysis confirmed the intracellular accumulation of PVC MNPs, with their peak fluorescence intensity outpacing that of PP across cellular layers. These findings suggest that the physicochemical properties of PVC and PP, such as surface charge and hydrophobicity, drive their differential interaction patterns. While both MNP types penetrate cells, PVC exhibits stronger affinity and uptake, potentially posing greater risks to endothelial integrity and vascular health. This study provides critical insights into the cellular effects of common environmental MNPs, emphasizing the need for further investigation into the biological effects and mechanisms of nanoparticle interactions with vascular cells to better assess their risk in maternal and fetal contexts. Ministry of Health, Italy by IRCCS - Burlo Garofolo (RC38/23)

1.09.C.T-03 Distribution of Micro- and Nanoplastics in Perfused Human Placental Tissue

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Although micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) have been found in numerous environmental and human samples, their fate and toxicity is still mostly unknown. As in utero exposure to environmental pollutants may adversely affect fetal health, assessing risks of MNPs to the unborn child is of utmost importance. Ex vivo placental perfusion is a unique system to gain insight into MNP particle size- and type-specific uptake, transport, localization, and quantification. Placentas were attached to a perfusion chamber with both fetal and maternal circulation. The placenta was perfused for a maximum of 6 h with 25 µg/mL of 50 nm, 200 nm, or 1 µm fluorescent polystyrene commercial spheres. Tissue pieces from before and after perfusion were collected, as well as the liquids in the maternal and fetal reservoir before and after perfusion. The perfused tissue was cryo-cut in slices of 30 µm thickness, and the slices were stained using SiR-actin to stain the actin components of the cells. The stained tissue slices were then analyzed with a Confocal Fluorescence Microscope (CFM). The perfusion solutions were measured with a spectrophotometer. Fluorescent polystyrene particles of all three sizes were found to be present in perfused placental tissue. The 50 nm and 200 nm particles seemed to agglomerate around the villi in the placental tissue, where transfer between maternal and fetal sides takes place. The 1 µm particles did not cluster and were found inside the villi. Fluorescence intensity measurements of the perfusion solutions showed limited transfer of all particle sizes to the fetal circulation, but loss of particles on the maternal